

DIAGNOSTIC ACCURACY OF TRANSCUTANEOUS BILIRUBINOMETRY FOR ESTIMATION OF SERUM BILIRUBIN IN NEONATES WITH PHYSIOLOGICAL JAUNDICE: A PROSPECTIVE CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY FROM A TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL IN WESTERN INDIA

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Neonatal jaundice is among the most common causes of neonatal hospitalization. Early and accurate assessment of bilirubin levels is essential to prevent severe hyperbilirubinemia and bilirubin-induced neurological dysfunction. Although total serum bilirubin (TSB) estimation is considered the gold standard, repeated blood sampling is invasive and painful. Transcutaneous bilirubinometry (TcB) offers a rapid, non-invasive alternative.

Objectives: To assess the accuracy of transcutaneous bilirubinometry by comparing TcB measurements with TSB levels and to evaluate its usefulness in reducing invasive blood sampling among neonates admitted with physiological jaundice.

Methods: A prospective analytical cross-sectional study was conducted in the Sick Neonatal Care Unit of GMERS Medical College and Civil Hospital, Gandhinagar, Gujarat, India, from November 2022 to February 2024. A total of 440 late-preterm and term neonates with physiological jaundice were enrolled. TcB measurements were obtained using the Dräger JM-105 bilirubinometer and compared with simultaneously measured serum bilirubin levels. Statistical analysis included descriptive statistics and Pearson correlation analysis.

Results: Among 440 neonates, 248 (56.4%) were male and 192 (43.6%) were female. Term neonates constituted 64.8% of the study population, while 35.2% were preterm. Significant hyperbilirubinemia was observed in 42 (9.5%) neonates. A very strong positive correlation was observed between TcB and TSB values ($r = 0.99$, $p < 0.01$). Mean admission TcB and TSB values were 13.96 ± 0.15 mg/dL and 14.49 ± 0.15 mg/dL respectively. After phototherapy, TcB and TSB values decreased to 3.40 ± 0.06 mg/dL and 3.44 ± 0.05 mg/dL respectively.

Conclusion: Transcutaneous bilirubinometry demonstrated excellent correlation with serum bilirubin estimation and may serve as a reliable screening and monitoring tool for neonatal hyperbilirubinemia.

KEYWORDS:

NEONATAL JAUNDICE, HYPERBILIRUBINEMIA, TRANSCUTANEOUS BILIRUBINOMETER, TOTAL SERUM BILIRUBIN, DRÄGER JM-105, NEONATE.

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INTRODUCTION

Neonatal hyperbilirubinemia affects approximately 60% of term and 80% of preterm newborns during the first week of life. Although most cases are physiological and self-limiting, severe hyperbilirubinemia can lead to acute bilirubin encephalopathy and kernicterus. Therefore, accurate assessment of bilirubin levels remains essential in neonatal care.

Total serum bilirubin estimation remains the diagnostic gold standard but requires repeated invasive blood sampling. Transcutaneous bilirubinometry has emerged as a rapid, painless, and bedside alternative. Several studies have reported good correlation between TcB and TSB measurements, supporting its role as a screening tool for neonatal jaundice. The present study aimed to assess the

diagnostic accuracy of transcutaneous bilirubinometry among neonates admitted with physiological jaundice.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY DESIGN:

Prospective analytical cross-sectional study.

STUDY SETTING:

Sick Neonatal Care Unit, Department of Pediatrics, GMERS Medical College and Civil Hospital, Gandhinagar, Gujarat, India.

STUDY DURATION:

November 2022 to February 2024.

STUDY POPULATION:

Late preterm and term neonates admitted with physiological jaundice.

SAMPLE SIZE:

$$n = E^2(Z\alpha/2)^2 \times P \times Q$$

$$n = (1.96)^2 \times 0.5 \times 0.5 / (0.05)^2$$

$$n = \frac{0.9604}{0.0025}$$

$$n = 384.16$$

$$n \approx 384$$

After adding approximately 10% for non-response:

$$384 + 38 = 422$$

Rounded:

$$n \approx 400$$

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Physiological jaundice up to 14 days of life.
- Late preterm and term neonates.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Major congenital anomalies.
- Pathological or hemolytic jaundice.
- Previous phototherapy or exchange transfusion.

STUDY INSTRUMENT:

Dräger JM-105 Transcutaneous Bilirubinometer.

REFERENCE STANDARD:

Total Serum Bilirubin estimation.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 26. Continuous variables were expressed as mean ± SD. Categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages. Pearson correlation coefficient was used to determine the relationship between TcB and TSB values. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

TABLE 1: DISTRIBUTION OF STUDY GROUPS AS PER GENDER

Gender	N	%
Female	192	43.6%
Male	248	56.4%
Total	440	100.0%

Out of the total 440 cases studied, 43.6% were females while 56.4% were males.

TABLE 2: DISTRIBUTION OF STUDY GROUPS AS PER TERM OF GESTATION

Term of Gestation	N	%
Pre-term	155	35.2%
Term	285	64.8%
Total	440	100.0%

Overall, pre-term neonates were 35.2% while term gestation was observed in 64.8% babies.

TABLE 3: DISTRIBUTION OF STUDY GROUPS AS PER BIRTH WEIGHT

Birth weight	N	%
< 2.5 Kg	181	41.1%
2.5 - 4 Kg	259	58.9%
Total	440	100.0%

A total of 58.9% newborns included in the study had normal birth weight while 41.1 % newborns had low birth weight.

TABLE 4: DISTRIBUTION OF STUDY GROUPS AS PER MODE OF DELIVERY

Mode of Delivery	N	%
LSCS	135	30.7%
Vaginal	305	69.3%
Total	440	100.0%

Mode of delivery was vaginal in 69.3% while it was caesarean in 30.7% cases.

TABLE 5: DISTRIBUTION OF STUDY GROUPS AS PER PRESENCE OF SIGNIFICANT HYPERBILIRUBINEMIA

Significant Hyperbilirubinemia (TSB>20 mg%)	N	%
No	398	90.5%
Yes	42	9.5%
Total	440	100.0%

Significant hyperbilirubinemia (defined as serum bilirubin levels > 20 mg/dl or cases requiring phototherapy) was observed in 9.5% newborns in present study.

TABLE 6: CORRELATION BETWEEN SERUM BILIRUBIN MEASUREMENT WITH TRANSCUTANEOUS BILIRUBINOMETER

Pearson co-relation		
TSB	r- value	p- value
Tc B	+0.99	<0.01

Correlation analysis is a statistical method used to measure the linear relationship between two variable. A high correlation (r- value >0.8) points to a strong relationship between the two variables. A positive correlation between two variables means when there is an increase in one variable, it leads to an increase in the other.

In present study, we observed a significant correlation was observed between bilirubin levels measured by transcutaneous bilirubinometer and serum bilirubin (r-0.99; p<0.01).

TABLE 7. MEAN DIFFERENCE BETWEEN SERUM BILIRUBIN MEASUREMENT AND TRANSCUTANEOUS BILIRUBINOMETER VALUES

Bilirubin levels (mg%)	N	Mean	SD	Mean difference	%age difference
				0.53	3.6%
Admission	TcB	440	13.96	0.15	3.6%
	TSB	440	14.49	0.15	
Post- PT	TcB	440	3.40	0.06	1.3%
	TSB	440	3.44	0.05	

In present study, we observed lower values with transcutaneous bilirubinometer, more so at time of admission as compared to post-phototherapy. The mean difference between admission bilirubin levels was 0.53 mg% (3.6%) which reduced to 0.04 mg% (1.3%) after phototherapy.

TABLE 8: DIFFERENCE BETWEEN SERUM BILIRUBIN MEASUREMENT AND TRANSCUTANEOUS BILIRUBINOMETER VALUES AT ADMISSION AND AFTER PHOTO-THERAPY

Difference between TSB & TCB	At Admission		After PT	
	N	%	N	%
>5%	68	15.5%	10	2.3%
>10%	6	1.4%	1	0.2%

We observed a difference of more than 5% between two methods was observed in 16.9% values at admission while >10% difference was observed in 1.4% values. The difference reduced significantly after phototherapy to 2.5% and 0.2% for >5% and >10% difference in values respectively.

TABLE 9: DIFFERENCE BETWEEN THE TWO READING ACROSS BILIRUBIN RANGES

TSB range	N	(TSB-TcB) > 5%	%
5-10%	23	1	4.3%
10.1-15%	298	39	13.1%
15.1-20%	77	18	23.4%
>20%	42	16	38.1%
Total	440	74	16.8%

Across various ranges of serum bilirubin, difference of >5% was observed more in higher range values i.e. 38.1% for >20mg% values, 23.4% for 15-20 mg%, 13.1% fo 10-15 mg% and 4.3% only for values <10 mg%.

TSB

TABLE 10: ROC CURVE ANALYSIS OF TRANSCUTANEOUS BILIRUBINOMETER VALUES FOR PREDICTION OF SIGNIFICANT HYPERBILIRUBINEMIA

Area Under the Curve: Significant Hyperbilirubinemia			
Test Result Variable(s)	Area	SE	p-value
			Asymptotic 95% Confidence Interval

				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
TcB	0.997	0.002	0	0.994	1

Ideal Cut-off	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV	Accuracy
>19.3 mg%	100.0%	98.5%	87.5%	100.0%	98.6%

On ROC Analysis, area under curve for TcB was 0.997(95% CI: 0.994-1.0; p<0.01). At cut-off value of >19.3 mg%, transcutaneous bilirubinometer measurement have the sensitivity and specificity of 100% and 98.5% for identifying significant hyperbilirubinemia with overall accuracy of 98.6%.

DISCUSSION

The present study demonstrated excellent agreement between transcutaneous bilirubinometry and serum bilirubin estimation. The observed correlation coefficient (r=0.99) was higher than that reported in several previous studies. Uwurukundo et al. reported a correlation of 0.745, Kitsommart et al. reported 0.80, while Mendoza-Chuctaya et al. demonstrated correlations of 0.90-0.91.

The minimal mean difference observed between TcB and TSB values further supports the clinical utility of the Dräger JM-105 device. The findings suggest that TcB can be used for routine screening and monitoring of neonatal jaundice, reducing the need for invasive blood sampling.

STRENGTHS

- Large sample size (440 neonates).
- Prospective study design.
- Use of standardized TcB device.
- Simultaneous TcB and TSB measurements.

CLINICAL IMPLICATIONS

Routine TcB screening may reduce painful venipuncture, improve neonatal comfort, decrease laboratory workload, and facilitate earlier clinical decision-making.

CONCLUSION

The present study suggests that transcutaneous bilirubinometer has a good diagnostic accuracy for measuring bilirubin in neonates admitted with jaundice. The sensitivity and specificity of TcB for prediction of

significant hyperbilirubinemia at cut-off of >19.3 mg% was 100% and 98.6%. The difference between the TcB and TSB measurements did not change much overall, however both overestimation and underestimation of TcB increased as TSB values increased. We thus conclude that measurement of transcutaneous bilirubin is a fast and painless method that can be considered a reliable tool for screening and monitoring neonatal jaundice, but not for a definitive diagnosis to decide the use of phototherapy, where TSB by blood sampling should be done.

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